

INTERETHNIC HARMONY AND RELIGIOUS TOLERANCE ARE THE HIGHEST VALUES OF THE UZBEK PEOPLE

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Abstract. *The article presents the attention paid to national policy in developing Uzbekistan's unique development path since the first years of independence, and the views on the legal foundations of maintaining interethnic stability in our country.*

Keywords: *interethnic harmony, harmony, international friendship, solidarity, tolerance, national experience, national development, New Uzbekistan, Development Strategy.*

Introduction

In Uzbekistan, under the leadership of the President of the country, effective measures are being implemented to strengthen the state sovereignty and territorial integrity of the Republic of Uzbekistan, further strengthen interethnic harmony and tolerance in society, preserve the ethnic and cultural identity of the peoples living in our country, and prevent discrimination regardless of gender, race, nationality, language, or religious affiliation and social origin.

Interethnic harmony is interethnic harmony, international friendship. Interethnic harmony is one of the main ideas of the ideology of national independence and is a concept that expresses the harmonious, joint, and cooperative activities of representatives of different nationalities in a certain territory or state without any conflicts. Interethnic harmony can be called the spiritual basis of mutual respect, kindness, friendship and solidarity between people of different nationalities and ethnicities living in one society and working towards a common goal. Not losing sight of common noble goals between nations is the basis for the development of ancient values.

Representatives of many nationalities and ethnicities have long lived in harmony on the territory of our country. There have been no national conflicts between them for centuries. Our people have always demonstrated such universal human qualities as tolerance, hospitality, forgiveness, respect for the traditions and values of others. Interethnic harmony is a universal value that determines the national development of regions and states where different peoples live together, and serves as a guarantee of peace and stability.

The hospitality and tolerance of the Uzbek people were especially manifested during the war years. During this period, more than 1 million people, including 200 thousand children, were evacuated to Uzbekistan. The Uzbek people treated orphans of different nationalities as their own and raised them. For example, the Shoahmad Shoahmudov family from Tashkent set a high example of humanism. During World War II, Shoahmad Shoahmudov and his wife Bahri Akramova adopted and educated abandoned and orphaned children of different nationalities. They took in 13 homeless children of different nationalities, and after the war, 3 more children. These were: Habiba, Vova, Shuhrat - Russian, Hamidulla - Ukrainian, Rafik, Rahmatulla - Tatar, Khalida - Moldovan, Samug' - Chuvash, Yuldosh, Ergash - Jewish, Halima - Kazakh, Karavoy, Ne'mat, Muazzam, Hakima, Ulug'bek - Uzbek.

The Shomahmudov's family, as a family that glorifies humanity, showed great courage and heroism. In a multinational country like Uzbekistan, harmonizing the interests of different nations

and ensuring harmony between them is one of the decisive factors of development. After all, the future of a nation is also connected with the development of other nations and countries, the situation and opportunities in the whole world. Without peace, tranquility, stability, solidarity, and equal relations among the peoples living side by side in the whole world, first of all, in neighboring countries, none of them can ensure its bright future.

The fact that currently in our country more than 130 nationalities and ethnic groups, 16 religious confessions, and more than 2,200 religious organizations live in peace and harmony, adhering to the principles of religious tolerance, is a clear evidence of our views. In addition, some areas of the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan are also aimed at improving harmonious interethnic relations.

One of the priority tasks of state policy in the field of interethnic relations is regular monitoring of the state of interethnic relations as a basis for early warning of possible disagreements and conflict situations in society and organizing activities to prevent them. In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev "On approval of the Concept of State Policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the Field of Interethnic Relations" (No. PF-5876), adopted on November 15, 2019, the following important aspects of the field are highlighted: - "In recent years, one of the priority areas of state policy has been to ensure interethnic harmony and tolerance in society, strengthen the atmosphere of friendship and the feeling of a large multinational single family, educate young people in the spirit of love and devotion to the Motherland, respect for national and universal values, and expand cultural and educational ties with foreign countries.

At present, the issue of preserving, further developing, and enriching the national traditions and values of different nations and peoples is constantly under the attention of our state. Today, general secondary education The fact that our schools provide education in 7 languages - Uzbek, Karakalpak, Russian, Kyrgyz, Turkmen, Kazakh and Tajik, as well as the fact that the mass media operate in 10 languages of the nationalities living in Uzbekistan, are a vivid example of this. The provisions of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan are being actively implemented in life, these provisions declare and guarantee that citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan, regardless of their nationality, constitute the people of Uzbekistan, as well as that the Republic of Uzbekistan will treat the language, customs and traditions of the nationalities and peoples living on its territory with respect, and create conditions for their development.

In particular, Article 13 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan states: - "Democracy in the Republic of Uzbekistan is based on universal human principles, according to which a person, his life, freedom, honor, dignity and other inalienable rights are considered the highest value." Article 19 of our Constitution states: "In the Republic of Uzbekistan, all citizens have the same rights and freedoms and are equal before the law, regardless of gender, race, nationality, language, religion, belief, social origin, or social status."

We are all proud that the rational policy pursued in our country towards ethnic harmony and religious tolerance is recognized by the world community. This, in turn, serves the peace and development of the country, the rise of universal culture and spirituality. It is no exaggeration to compare our country with many families of different nationalities and ethnicities. The diversity of the population in Uzbekistan is a favorable factor for socio-economic development. In particular, education in state educational institutions of our country is conducted in seven languages. The National Television and Radio Company of Uzbekistan broadcasts in twelve languages, and newspapers and magazines are published in more than ten languages.

The Committee for Interethnic Relations and Friendship with Foreign Countries has 138 national-cultural centers, as well as about 2,300 religious organizations belonging to 16 confessions. We sincerely believe that these factors contribute to the development of Uzbekistan. Many of our compatriots are unaware of the existence of a center in our country that is engaged in strengthening and studying interethnic relations. The “Baynalminal” center, founded in January 1992 by the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, is still operating. The meaning of the term “Baynalminal” is the Arabic translation of the word “international” and has an interethnic meaning. The task of this center is to coordinate the activities of national cultural centers operating in our country, provide them with practical and methodological assistance. Today, this cultural center coordinates the activities of about 140 national cultural centers. Our great scholars have delivered many speeches on this topic and have always amazed representatives of all nationalities with the tolerance of the Uzbek people and these beautiful qualities that are deeply embedded in our culture and identity.

In particular, Sheikh Abdulaziz Mansur, at the 2017 event on the topic of “The social significance of the tolerance and noble qualities of the Uzbek people,” emphasized that Islam is a religion of tolerance based on the idea of respect for other religions and encourages all people to be kind and compassionate, regardless of their religion. During the visit of the UN High Commissioner for Human Rights Zeid Ra'ad Al Hussein and the High Commissioner on National Minorities of the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe Lamberto Zannier, reforms and changes in this regard were discussed. Highly appreciated. It is noteworthy that in 2017, for the first time in the history of independent Uzbekistan, the UN Human Rights Council Special Rapporteur on religion and belief, Ahmad Shahid, visited our country. Based on his recommendations, on May 4, 2018, the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan approved the "Roadmap" for ensuring freedom of religion and belief.

In general, the international community highly appreciates the activities of our country in ensuring interethnic harmony and religious tolerance and is interested in the experience of Uzbekistan. In particular, on September 19, 2017, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev called for the establishment of tolerance and mutual respect, ensuring freedom of religious belief, and protecting the rights of believers at the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly. The proposal for a special resolution entitled “Enlightenment and Religious Tolerance” on December 12, 2018, the non-discrimination and the adoption of this document on December 12, 2018 are a vivid example of this. One of the important results of reforms in this regard is that in 2018, the US Department of State removed Uzbekistan from the list of “countries of particular concern” regarding religious freedom.

CONCLUSION

In order to ensure these rights of citizens, the Committee on Interethnic Relations and Friendship with Foreign Countries was established under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which carries out its activities and consistently implements the state policy on ensuring interethnic harmony and tolerance in society.

Attention to interethnic harmony creates the basis for the nations and peoples living in Uzbekistan to engage in various professions and become aware of customs and traditions. This directly leads to the development and further enrichment of spiritual values within the nation.

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